

On the value and potential of demand response in the Smart island archipelago

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Abstract

Existing studies propose different demand response models and often test them on islands that represent test-beds for new technologies. However, proposed models are often simplified and integrated into energy system models that do not consider the existing limitations of the power grid. This study proposes a novel demand response model based on price differentials on the day-ahead electricity market. The model is implemented in the distribution system that considers all relevant grid constraints. The case study is conducted in an archipelago characterised by a medium-voltage distribution system connected to the mainland grid. The obtained results showed that the implementation of the proposed demand response model caused a 0.13 kV voltage deviation which did not cause voltage issues for the observed distribution system. The breakpoint incentive was achieved for an incentive value of 23% of the day-ahead market, and the demand response was not activated for higher values than the breakpoint incentive. The highest savings amounted to 258.7 € for the scenario with the highest flexibility allowed. The results implicate that implementing the demand response model in the grid would benefit all observed stakeholders in the system.

Keywords

Smart islands, Demand response, Renewable energy sources, energy system analysis, energy flexibility, Integrated energy system

1. Introduction

The objectives set by the European Union for a rapid increase of renewable energy sources (RES) pose new challenges for the existing power systems. Variable RES such as solar and wind power constantly change their power output that depends on the weather conditions. Such changes create the potential for introducing new technologies such as energy storage and demand response. These technologies can tackle the variability issue and assure the highest possibility for RES integration with generated benefit for the consumers in the energy system. Testing mentioned technologies is increasingly conducted on geographical islands through a concept known as “living labs” based on the idea that successful integration of demand response on the islands can effectively be implemented on the mainland as well [1].

Successful cross-system integration represents a necessity in order to achieve local smart energy systems [2]. In this context, local action is necessary in order to successfully transit to decarbonised energy systems, as stated in [3]. Several studies presented smart energy system concepts on islands. For example, the authors in [4] analysed the energy transition possibilities of Madeira island by investigating the market flexibility requirements with the conclusion that the inclusion of customers in the market is necessary for a successful energy transition. Another example is a generation expansion planning for Santiago Island, Cape Verde [5], where the importance of sector integration for a 100% renewable island was also highlighted. Hybrid solutions consisted of hydrogen, batteries, and RES also present a solution for the islanded microgrids [6]. Battery storage systems can represent another flexibility source and can provide ancillary services by applying concepts such as in [7].

Recent studies focus their research on demand-side management strategies for two main reasons. Firstly, the development of the electric energy markets is starting to enable broader possibilities for demand-side management. Secondly, increased efforts are being invested by the EU to enable customer participation in the electricity market [8]. Thus, as the DR is

becoming more critical in the field of energy research, authors debate about the benefits and the drawbacks of different DR implementations.

A review of the DR model is provided in [9]. The author has explained different DR models with emphasis on different incentive and pricing models for its optimal integration. In order to implement the DR, it is necessary to integrate smart technology such as smart meters, sensors and control units in the grid and at the DR providers. Such technology is available today, and the study [10] presents an overview of different DR possibilities and devices necessary for its implementation. Blockchain platforms that enable DR service were also recently developed [11].

The DR potential assessment is provided in [12], where the author concluded that the hourly average for demand reduction in Europe amounts to 93 GW. In comparison, the average for demand retrieval (an increase of the demand) has amounted to 247 GW. These studies [10] and [12] do not consider any specific mathematical model of the DR implementation. Residential customers' acceptance of the DR technology is one of the main necessities for implementing the DR programs, as highlighted in [13]. Authors found that, on average, a single customer would be willing to invest 150 € in devices that would enable the DR.

Authors in [14] applied the DR at a Dutch case study. They concluded that the DR cuts electricity system costs between 2.4 and 6.3 billion euros, where the electricity market cost, as well as the grid development costs, were considered. However, the grid constraints were modelled only as maximum active power allowed, and the DR model did not impose the constraints that consider the DR feedback effect. Priority banking incentive mechanism was presented in [15], and it showed that savings of 1.57\$ for a particular load during one day are possible; however, the study did not conduct sensitivity analysis of more flexibility levels as well as technical impacts on the observed grid.

A detailed review of battery storage and DR solutions was provided in a recent study [16]. The authors stated several demand-side management implementation possibilities with an emphasis on the integration of electricity, water and transport sector as well as power-to-heat technologies. The authors in particular mentioned the cooling sector as a flexibility provider for the islands. Moreover, the locations with high hydropower resource can use district heating systems as a flexibility provider [17]. The heat storage models presented in [18] can also increase the flexibility if they would be connected to the grid and DR programme.

Dorotić et al. [19] presented a possibility for providing the DR by using smart charging of EV and suggested that it is possible to reduce the energy import from 11 GWh to 6.5 GWh on the island of Korčula. However, this study used the simulation approach and did not consider the conditions in the existing distribution grid. Another study was conducted on Dongfushan Island [20], where authors showed that an 81.98\$ fuel saving is possible when the DR is implemented, but the study does not analyse the DR impact on technical conditions in the grid, nor it defines different levels of flexibility.

A multi-energy microgrid with flexible demand was modelled in [21], where authors underlined that the curtailment of variable RES is 3.25% lower when different sectors are coupled together with flexible demand. The study [21], however, does not consider compensation for the customers that provide flexible demand, nor it considers distribution system grid. Meschede, H. et al. [22] analysed the case for Canary islands and introduced a self-sufficiency indicator that increases by 1.8% when the DR is introduced; however, this study also did not model technical grid characteristics. The parameters that are used for distribution system modelling are voltage amount and angle, current, resistance, reactance, susceptance, and bus type, together with all limitation parameters. Another study conducted on islands used the domestic hot water for providing the DR in the [23], and authors showed that total dispatch cost reduces from 0% to 0.8% when DR is used in comparison to a scenario without the DR. However, the DR modelling in [23] is limited to domestic hot water and the economic dispatch model that neglects the distribution system constraints.

A novel soft-linking approach of the models where flexibility was represented based on temperature values in the district heating system was presented in [24] with the conclusion that it is possible to achieve a 5.4% savings in the district heating system for the best-case scenario, but the study focuses only on district heating system. A similar study [25] with a non-linear DR model was conducted on a case study where water towers are used for supplying the three cities with enough water and with high enough temperature with the conclusion that it is possible to reduce the operation cost of towers for 4.1% when the DR model is introduced. Authors of [26] presented a cost-benefit analysis of applying the DR in the energy system; however, without consideration of the power grid parameters and concluded that the operation cost reduces by 1.17% for the scenario with the DR in comparison to the scenario without DR. Zhang et al. [27] present a DR model considering elasticity of the market and states that, for real-time pricing scheme, total revenue during 24h from the DR is 88 € for observed region although this study does not consider technical characteristics of the grid.

In [28], customer and utility benefit functions were introduced for the DR with the conclusion that possible revenue can amount to 371\$ for three customers for 24 hours when the DR is included in the system operation. However, the study does not define the DR retrieval but only the load shedding. The authors in [29] presented the energy system model of several interconnected islands with an integrated DR model in the form of V2G and showed that the DR could enable the integration of variable RES up to 85.6% of the primary energy supply. However, the result of this study was based on the simulation model, not an optimisation one. Overview of the simulation strategies for enabling the DR is provided in [30] with the remark that the structure of the presented models could be improved with properties of the optimisation models. The main advantage of the optimisation model over simulation one is that it finds the best possible values of decision variables for minimising or maximising the given objective function. The simulation model observes specific case and does not minimise or maximise the objective function.

The study [31] emphasises the need for a more detailed representation of the DR and the energy system models, as many current studies include only simplistic models. Most of the DR is provided by the users connected to the low-voltage (LV) and medium-voltage (MV) distribution network. Thus, it is necessary to include distribution system elements and limitations in order to observe the complete influence of the DR model. An example of such representation of a distribution system is provided in [32]. The application of non-linear programming (NLP) is one of the possibilities for solving DR optimisation problems where every node in the electricity grid has the option of controlling its load, as stated in [33]. However, the authors do not emphasise the limitations of such an approach. The main limitation is that such a model would be computationally complex for large systems and would not guarantee the global optimum. Ghasemi, A. et al. [34] concluded that PHP has better performance than the DR as the economic performance index is higher by 1.6% for the PHP. However, the study used a simple DR model and did not include the DR cost in the objective function. Ajoulabadi et al. [35] presented an optimisation framework that includes the DR program for four cases of user participation and achieves the reduction of operation cost by 1.2% for the case when all customers are part of the DR program. The study, however, does not include the cost of DR in the objective function that minimises the total operation cost. Implementation of the DR in [36] resulted in the system operating cost reduction of 62\$, but the study introduces a simplified DR model, without the DR retrieval constraints, that is based only on estimated DR potential.

Analysed studies mostly used simplified DR models that consider only load curtailment without energy retrieval, or the models did not impose constraints between the curtailed and retrieved energy. This assumption can be valid if analysed loads are lights, for example. However, the biggest DR potential lies with the heating and cooling devices, and their inclusion in DR programs results in higher energy consumption. This study introduces a novel DR model formulation based on price differential on the day-ahead electricity market with modelled constraints for the DR retrieval that assures energy preservation in the system. Secondly, most studies use simulations or simple optimisation formulations that neglect the realistic constraints that exist in the grid and limitations that are imposed by the DSO. These approaches cannot observe the technical impact that is provoked by the DR event. The present study includes the proposed DR model in the energy system with all relevant grid parameters, as well as the limitations set by the DSO. Thus, the proposed approach allows the research of technical parameters as well. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no reference to such a DR model implemented in the distribution system grid.

The hypothesis of this paper is that, by using the presented mathematical model of the DR incorporated in the small radial distribution system with modelled all steady-state grid parameters, it is possible to generate revenue for nodal stakeholders and reduce operating costs as well as assess the impact of the DR on the technical parameters of the power system. The contributions of this paper are listed below:

- A novel mathematical model of DR that includes customers in the day-ahead electricity market and aims at operation cost reduction as well as revenue generation for customers
- Energy system optimisation model that considers technical grid parameters and includes the proposed DR model. The model reflects the technical changes in the system operation and ensures that the limitations set by the DSO are not violated.
- Sensitivity analysis of the DR model when the model is placed in the uncertain market conditions for different flexibility levels and different DR incentive values
- The impact assessment of different flexibility levels and incentive values on the energy system operation parameters
- The study contributes to the overall investigation and unlocking of the power system flexibility by proposing a novel DR model

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: the second section presents a method with the DR model and the energy system in which it is included. The third section describes the case study, after which follows results and discussion. The conclusion is provided in the fifth section.

2. Methods and materials

This paper presents a novel DR mathematical model integrated into an energy system model that is described with grid parameters where constraints that are imposed by the DSO are implemented. The DR model is designed in such a way that it uses the price differential between the two consecutive hours on the electricity day-ahead market as a basis for determining the quantity of provided DR. The model aims at exploiting the price changes on the electricity market in order to minimise operational cost and generate revenue for the consumers. It is assumed that the DR model is used within the small radial distribution system. As stated in the literature review, many studies do not analyse grid conditions when new technology is implemented, which can significantly limit the model.

Since the DR model was implemented in the radial distribution system, there is a possibility for voltage deviation because of a change in the power flows. Thus, the new voltage values, that will occur as a result of a DR, should be calculated so that it can be determined whether there was a voltage violation or not. For example, if there is a high VRES production and high market prices at the same time, the algorithm may optimize the operation so that it shifts demand from those periods which would cause additional voltage increase. This is particularly important for the radial distribution systems that already have significant voltage deviations as a result of a high VRES share.

The study assumes that the distribution system operator (DSO) is responsible for system operation. The DSO can control the demand at each node to the extent that model permits. The DR providers are consumers that have the possibility and technical conditions for providing the DR, while the DR users are all consumers in the archipelago.

2.1. System modelling

The energy system is defined as a feasible non-linear optimisation problem with objective function f . The objective function is represented with equation (1):

$$\min f \triangleq \min[\sum_{t \in \Omega_T} (\lambda_t \cdot E_{slack,t} + \mu \cdot \varphi_{i,t}^- \cdot L_{i,t}^P + CPV \cdot E_{CPV,t})], \quad \forall i \in \Omega_N \quad (1)$$

Where μ represents the incentive that is paid by the operator to the DR provider. DR providers are households with their appliances as well as other facilities such as desalination plants which are often present on the islands. The incentive for providing the DR can be expressed as a function or constant value. For implementation reasons, the most straightforward possibility would be to choose a constant value or simple linear function for the representation of the DR incentive.

However, more complex functions can also be modelled in order to determine the incentive. $\varphi_{i,t}^-$ is the DR function (16) and $L_{i,t}^P$ is the load at bus i at time t . CPV is the penalty for the curtailed PV energy and $E_{CPV,t}$ is the actual curtailed energy from PV. λ_t represents the current price of electric energy on the day-ahead market. $E_{slack,t}$ is the amount of electricity that is imported or exported to or from the observed grid through the point of common coupling with the remainder of the system.

The constraints for this optimisation problem are based on real limitations imposed by the distribution grid and the DR providers. They form the NLP model which is solved in GAMS with a CONOPT solver suited for non-linear problems, especially small-scale problems. Active power flow $P_{ij,t}$ between busses i and j are given with equation (2). Reactive power flow $Q_{ij,t}$ between busses i and j is given with equation (3). Apparent power flow $S_{ij,t}$ is defined according to equation (4). It is worth noting that the power transmitted from bus $i \in \Omega_N$ through the line $ij \in \Omega_\epsilon$ will not equal the power transmitted to the bus $j \in \Omega_N$ which corresponds with existing physical conditions in the grid. That is to say, that $P_{ij,t} \neq -P_{ji,t}$ and $Q_{ij,t} \neq -Q_{ji,t}$ for $\forall t \in \Omega_T$, $\forall i \in \Omega_N$ and $\forall ij \in \Omega_\epsilon$.

Apparent power flow is limited with upper and lower values, presented with equation (5) and is a characteristic of the maximum allowable current for a specific line or cable. Current $I_{ij,t}$ is defined with voltages between busses i and j and the impedance of the line connecting these two busses (6). Active and reactive power balance must be assured in every timestep t . These constraints are expressed with equations (7) and (8). It is worth noting that the DR model is

considered in the equations for active and reactive power and has an influence on both parameters. The voltage on a particular node is denoted with $V_{i,t}$ for voltage level and $\delta_{i,t}$ for voltage angle, while the line parameters are given with the impedance parameters Z_{ij} , θ_{ij} and susceptance b . Voltage $V_{i,t}$ and voltage angle $\delta_{i,t}$ are limited with their upper and lower values (9) and (10). Equations (2) – (10) are valid for $\forall t \in \Omega_{\mathcal{T}}$, $\forall i \in \Omega_{\mathcal{N}}$ and $\forall ij \in \Omega_{\varepsilon}$.

$$P_{ij,t} = \frac{V_{i,t}^2}{Z_{ij}} \cos(\theta_{ij}) - \frac{V_{i,t}V_{j,t}}{Z_{ij}} \cos(\delta_{i,t} - \delta_{j,t} + \theta_{ij}) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{ij,t} = \frac{V_{i,t}^2}{Z_{ij}} \sin(\theta_{ij}) - \frac{V_{i,t}V_{j,t}}{Z_{ij}} \sin(\delta_{i,t} - \delta_{j,t} + \theta_{ij}) - \frac{bV_{i,t}^2}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$S_{ij,t} = (V_{i,t} \angle \delta_{i,t}) I_{ij,t}^* \quad (4)$$

$$-S_{ij,max} < S_{ij,t} < S_{ij,max} \quad (5)$$

$$I_{ij,t} = \frac{V_{i,t} \angle \delta_{i,t} - V_{j,t} \angle \delta_{j,t}}{Z_{ij} \angle \theta_{ij}} + \frac{bV_{i,t}}{2} \angle \left(\delta_{i,t} + \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$P_{slack,t} + P_{i,t}^{PV} + P_{i,t}^d + P_{i,t}^c - (1 + \varphi_t^+ - \varphi_t^-) L_{i,t}^P = \sum_{j \in \Omega_i^i} P_{ij,t} \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{slack,t} + Q_{i,t}^{PV} + Q_{i,t}^d + Q_{i,t}^c - (1 + \varphi_t^+ - \varphi_t^-) L_{i,t}^Q = \sum_{j \in \Omega_i^i} Q_{ij,t} \quad (8)$$

$$V_{min} \leq V_{i,t} \leq V_{max} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_{min} \leq \delta_{i,t} \leq \delta_{max} \quad (10)$$

A constraint for the PV plant is provided with equation (9) for $\forall t \in \Omega_{\mathcal{T}}$ and $\forall i \in \Omega_{PV}$. The sum of the PV production and the curtailed production from PV should be equal to the total possible PV production $\Lambda_{i,t}^{PV}$. It is assumed that the PV plant operates with $\cos\varphi = 1$.

$$P_{i,t}^{PV} + P_{i,t}^{CPV} = \Lambda_{i,t}^{PV} \quad (11)$$

The electrical energy storage system (ESS) is provided with a standard model consisted of SOC equation and limits as well as maximum charging and discharging possibility in a given period. Similarly to the PV plant, it is assumed that the ESS can only discharge and charge active power. The battery model is given with equations (12) – (15) for $\forall t \in \Omega_{\mathcal{T}}$ and $\forall i \in \Omega_{ESS}$.

$$SOC_{i,t} = SOC_{i,t-1} + (P_{i,t}^c \cdot \eta_c - \frac{P_{i,t}^d}{\eta_d}) \cdot \Delta t \quad (12)$$

$$SOC_i^{min} \leq SOC_{i,t} \leq SOC_i^{max} \quad (13)$$

$$P_{i,t}^c \cdot \Delta t \leq \beta_i \cdot SOC_i^{max}, \beta_i \in [0,1] \quad (14)$$

$$P_{i,t}^d \cdot \Delta t \leq \beta_i \cdot SOC_i^{min}, \beta_i \in [0,1] \quad (15)$$

2.2. Demand response model

The DR model is based on the price difference between two consecutive hours. The higher the differential of these two values, the higher value of the DR is achieved. This is implemented by defining function $\varphi(\lambda_t, \lambda_{t-1})$. Mathematical expression for the defined function is given with (16) – (18) for $\forall t \in \Omega_T$ and $\forall i \in \Omega_{DR}$.

$$\varphi_{i,t}^- \begin{cases} \leq \tanh \frac{2(\lambda_t - \lambda_{t-1})}{k(\lambda_t + \lambda_{t-1})}, \lambda_t - \lambda_{t-1} > 0 \\ = 0, \text{ else} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$\varphi_{i,t}^+ \begin{cases} \leq \tanh \frac{2(\lambda_{t-1} - \lambda_t)}{k(\lambda_t + \lambda_{t-1})}, \lambda_t - \lambda_{t-1} \leq 0 \\ = 0, \text{ else} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_t^T \varphi_{i,t}^+ \cdot L_{i,t}^P = \vartheta \sum_t^T \varphi_{i,t}^- \cdot L_{i,t}^P \quad (18)$$

where $k \in [0,1]$ is a coefficient that enables more or less flexibility. The value of factor k is dependent on the number of loads that are used for providing the DR in the distribution grid. More flexible heating or cooling devices, desalination plants, etc. would result in a higher possibility for providing the DR. An exact method for defining a single value of factor k is out of the scope of this paper; however, a detailed sensitivity analysis of the impact its value as will be further elaborated in the Results and discussion section.

$\varphi_{i,t}^- \in [0,1]$ represents the DR coefficient at each node in a particular time, while the $\varphi_{i,t}^+ \in [0,1]$ represents the DR retrieval coefficient. Multiplication of coefficients with the load at each node in the given time results with the exact DR and DR retrieval values. Factor ϑ is used as a representation of the efficiency of the DR. It depends on the types of loads that are present in the distribution grid. For example, the value for heating or cooling devices can be over 1, while for the lights, this value is 0. The zero value of ϑ would also result in a one-way DR or only load shedding.

The DR model aims at reflecting the differential between two consecutive day-ahead market prices. If price differential was divided only with the current market price, the model would be asymmetrical as the values for $\varphi_{i,t}^-$ and $\varphi_{i,t}^+$ would be different for the same price difference. Thus, the price difference is divided with their summation in order to achieve symmetry between $\varphi_{i,t}^-$ and $\varphi_{i,t}^+$ values.

As factor k is introduced, for small values of k there is a possibility that the value of $\varphi_{i,t}^-$ and $\varphi_{i,t}^+$ exceeds available demand. Thus, there is a need for limitation of $\varphi_{i,t}^-$ and $\varphi_{i,t}^+$ values which is one of the reasons why the hyperbolic tangent is used.

The first suitable characteristic of this function is that it is continuous and symmetric within its domain, meaning that $\tanh(-x) = -\tanh(x)$. Such characteristic allows DR in two directions, increasing and decreasing power in times when required. Another characteristic of this function is $\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} (\tanh(x)) = -1$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} (\tanh(x)) = 1$ meaning that hyperbolic tangent limits values to a range or $\tanh(x): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [-1,1]$. Because of this characteristic, high positive or negative values of the price differential value do not result in high DR or DR retrieval that may cause financial, technical or social repercussions that may occur as it is assumed that the DR is mandatory for all observed nodes i . For example, too high a request for an increase in the power issued as a result of a significant negative differential of price may cause grid issues, and result in high costs for the operator or cause overloads of devices and utilities that provide the DR service. By limiting their values with $\tanh(x)$ function, this is avoided.

On the other hand, as Taylor series of a hyperbolic tangent is expressed with $\tanh(x) \approx x - \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{2x^5}{15} - \dots$, the values of the small price differentials are linearised and the value of the functions $\varphi_{i,t}^-$ and $\varphi_{i,t}^+$ is proportional to the price differential. This means that, for small price changes, it is possible to write $\tanh\left[\frac{2(\lambda_t - \lambda_{t-1})}{k(\lambda_t + \lambda_{t-1})}\right] \approx \left[\frac{2(\lambda_t - \lambda_{t-1})}{k(\lambda_t + \lambda_{t-1})}\right]$. The DR model presented in this paper is a price-taker model, meaning that it does not participate in price forming on the market.

Following decision variables (X), parameters (P) and sets (S) are defined:

$$X = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} E_{slack,t}, \varphi_{i,t}^-, \varphi_{i,t}^+, E_{i,t}^{CPV}, \\ Q_{slack,t}, V_{i,t}, \delta_{i,t}, I_{ij,t}, P_{i,t}^d, P_{i,t}^c, SOC_{i,t}, \\ P_{i,t}^{PV}, Q_{i,t}^{PV}, Q_{i,t}^c, Q_{i,t}^d \end{array} \right\}$$

$$P = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mu, CPV, SOC_i^{min/max}, Z_{ij}, \\ \theta_{ij}, \eta_c, \eta_d, L_{i,t}^P, L_{i,t}^Q, \\ \lambda_t, \beta_i, \Lambda_i^{PV}, S_{ij,max} \end{array} \right\}$$

$$S = \{\Omega_T, \Omega_N, \Omega_\varepsilon, \Omega_{ESS}, \Omega_{DR}, \Omega_{PV}\}$$

Prices on the day-ahead electricity market are uncertain for many reasons such as variability of the demand, PV and wind power plant installations, price-makers competitions, grid losses etc. Since the proposed DR model is dependent on market prices, this study investigated the model operation under different market scenarios. Operation cost over time, DR model operation, voltage vector and ESS operation with DR model are parameters examined under the different price scenarios. The complete overview of the proposed method is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The proposed method for implementation of the DR model

3. Case study

3.1. Analysed scenarios

The proposed method is applied to the case of the Kvarner archipelago in Croatia. The considered islands are Lošinj, Cres with three locations Osor, Hrasta and PV plant Orlec, Male Srkane, Vele Srkane, Susak and Unije. The complete topology of the system with the names of the bus is presented in Figure 2. The number of the bus is represented by the number by the name of the bus. A geographical overview of the archipelago is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 2. The topology of the power system of the Kvarner archipelago

Figure 3. A geographical overview of the analysed archipelago - red line represents a 110 kV line to the mainland grid

The data for grid modelling is provided in [37]. Substation (1) was modelled as a slack bus connecting the archipelago with the rest of the grid. This is possible because this substation is equipped with an automatic transformer 110/35/10 kV and has a 110 kV connection to the Melina substation 400/220/110 kV on the mainland (over the Krk substation). Hydropower plants Senj (216 MW) and Vinodol (90 MW) are connected to Melina 220 kV buses and are able to provide the required spinning reserve and regulation necessary to maintain the grid stability. However, they cannot ensure that voltage in the radial distribution grid is within the allowed limits; thus, voltage values were calculated in this study.

Data about the active and reactive load is available from measurements at the main substation for every hour on the summer day when the maximum load is present. Demand on smaller substations is obtained by scaling measured load values from the main substation. Demand values are given in Figure 4 as a ratio of the load at time t and the maximum load. Prices of electric energy are obtained from CROPEX day-ahead market for the day of maximum load.

Values of all parameters are given in Table 1. This study considered only PV as a VRES according to the existing plans and projects for the observed case study. As mentioned in the method section, incentive μ can be represented as a function or a constant value. This study analysed several possibilities for incentive value. Such implementation would be simple enough for realisation once the EU directive [8], which sets the objective that every retail buyer has access to the hourly prices, is implemented. Energy efficiency is specific for a given case study, and it depends on types of the loads that are present in the observed system. Detailed mapping of different load types was not part of this study, but there are no special industries or larger facilities in the archipelago. However, it can be assumed that there is a larger amount of heating and cooling devices due to warmer climate conditions. Thus it was assumed that the factor ϑ is equal to 1.1. ESS parameters values are specific for the examined case study as foreseen in [38].

Figure 4. Load at every hour of a summer day

Table 1. The values of parameters used in the model

Name	Value	Name	Value
μ [€/MWh]	$0.1\lambda_t$	η_c	0.95
CPV [€/MWh]	150	η_d	0.9
β	0.25	ϑ	1.1
SOC_i^{min} [€/MWh]	0.16	SOC_i^{max} [€/MWh]	1.44
P_{max} [MW]	20.77		

It is considered that the PV and ESS operate with $\cos \varphi = 1$, thus only active power from PV and ESS is considered while the reactive power values are equal to zero. The maximum PV output on Unije is equal to 1 MW, and on Orlec, it is equal to 4.14. The ESS capacity is equal to 1.6 MWh. In this study, several scenarios were considered:

- 1) *Scenario A*: This scenario represents the base case with the PV plants and without the possibility for DR and ESS. This scenario is subject to load flow constraints and is used as a benchmark case. It also represents a simpler problem as the objective function is to minimise the cost of system operation without consideration of DR. The decision variables are $X_A = \{E_{slack,t}, E_{i,t}^{CPV}, Q_{slack,t}, V_{i,t}, \delta_{i,t}, I_{ij,t}, P_{i,t}^{PV}\}$
- 2) *Scenario B*: This scenario considers the same conditions as in scenario A but with added ESS. Scenario B was used for the assessment of ESS on the power system and also for comparison purposes to DR. The decision variables considered for this scenario are $X_B = X_A \cup \{P_{i,t}^d, P_{i,t}^c, SOC_{i,t}\}$.
- 3) *Scenario C*: Scenario C considers the base scenario with the possibility for DR in the archipelago. Comparison of scenario C to scenario B was conducted in order to assess the benefits of both technologies. The decision variables for this scenario are $X_C = X_A \cup \{\varphi_{i,t}^+, \varphi_{i,t}^-\}$
- 4) *Scenario D*: Final scenario considered the inclusion of both ESS and DR. This scenario was used to assess the joint impact of both technologies and considers all presented decision variables $X_D = X_B \cup X_C$.

3.2. PV share influence

Within this case study, the impact of different PV share will be assessed in order to observe the overall system operation when the different level of variable production is present. In order to conduct this analysis, buses 3 and 7 were also modelled as the buses with the PV plant. This approach is taken in order to avoid high PV curtailment values that would occur if all the production would be placed in buses 4 and 13. Operation cost, curtailed PV production values, voltage, ESS and DR operation were observed under different flexibility and PV share values.

3.3. Market price modelling

In order to model prices on the electricity market, data from the Croatian power market [39] was used. The probabilistic behaviour of electricity market prices was modelled by using the normal probability distribution function (PDF) given with equation (17). The objective of this approach is to assess the DR model behaviour when placed in different market price scenarios as the level of future market prices is highly uncertain.

$$PDF(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{\left(-\frac{(x-\bar{z})^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} \quad (17)$$

In equation (17), σ represents the standard deviation and \bar{z} mean value of observed data. Similarly, as in referenced studies, a discretised normal distribution was used by considering five scenarios. This simplification was used in order to reduce computation time that can be extensive when a continuous normal distribution is used. With the proposed approach, all scenario values fall into the 95.44% probability range or two-sigma probability. Prices were modelled according to price values during peak demand that occurs in July and August.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Scenarios overview

1) *Scenario A*: Total operating cost amounted to 18,665.2 € (mean), with the total amount of imported electricity equal to 333.95 MWh (mean). The total operating cost for this scenario varies from 14,081.91 € (-2σ) to 23,247.56 € (2σ).

2) *Scenario B*: This scenario assumes that the ESS is connected to a bus 13 without the

possibility for the DR in the system and the operating costs for this scenario are 18,657.2 € (mean) with the total imported electricity equal to 334.13 MWh (mean). Figure 5 shows the operation of the ESS from which it can be seen that the ESS is active during the night hours when it is charging and in the evening when it is discharging.

Figure 5. Operation of the ESS in scenario B

It can be observed in Figure 6 that the ESS can have an impact on the technical aspects of the system, such as voltage. In this case, where the ESS operation is determined by the market price, the ESS lowers the voltage toward nominal value during the night hours and increases it in the evening hours.

Figure 6. The voltage at node 13 for scenario A and B

- 3) *Scenario C*: Scenario C considers the possibility for the DR in the analysed system without ESS. The results showed that the operating cost for this scenario is 18,659.75 € (mean) with 333.08 MWh of imported electricity. Figure 7 presents the DR operation for scenario C and ESS charge and discharge for scenario B for lowest flexibility ($k = 1$). It is obvious that the DR model is operating differently than the ESS, which is a consequence of the fact that the DR is dependent on consecutive price differences on the day-ahead market while the ESS operation is dependent on low and high prices.

Thus, it is possible to observe a prolonged ESS operation during the night and evening hours, while the DR is active during several periods over the day as well.

Figure 7. The operation of the DR in scenario C and ESS in scenario B – the charging of the ESS is represented with the positive sign while the discharging is represented with a negative sign as the objective of the figure is to show the values about their impact on the demand of the system

- 4) *Scenario D*: Final scenario considers the operation of both the ESS and the DR. Total operating cost of scenario D is 18,651.8 € (mean), and the total imported electricity is equal to 334.27 MWh (mean). The operation cost for this scenario varies from 14,066.46 € (-2σ) to 23,181.21 € (2σ). Additional analysis was conducted for this scenario by changing the flexibility parameter k . The lower value of the k parameter allows more possibility for higher amounts of DR. Regardless of the difference in consecutive prices on the market, and the hyperbolic tangent function prevents that possible DR amount exceeds node demand, as explained previously.

The total cost of the scenario varies from 18,651.8 € ($k = 1$) to 18,607.78 € ($k = 0.1$). The total cost does not change significantly for the lowest levels of flexibility, but it decreases as more flexibility is introduced in the system. Imported electricity increases from 334.27 MWh in original scenario D ($k = 1$) to 335.8 MWh ($k = 0.1$). The imported electricity for all scenarios and flexibility levels does not change for more than 0.56% of initial scenario A achieved for scenario D and the highest modelled flexibility. This result is expected as it was modelled with equations (17) and (18) that demand has to be retrieved. Moreover, the operation cost with implemented DR does not change significantly in comparison to the original scenario A, which is also expected due to the demand retrieval, as well as, in the D scenario, the additional cost is revenue for DR providers. Nevertheless, the overall benefit is increased as cost reduces for all DR

scenarios and the revenue of DR providers increase. Changes in savings and imported electricity are illustrated in Figures 8 and 9, where the impact of DR model behaviour can be observed over the entire time.

Figure 8. Operation cost for different flexibility levels

Figure 9. Electricity import for different flexibility levels

The DR operation is presented in Figure 10. It is possible to observe that the demand is reduced during evening hours and during the day, while it is retrieved during night hours. The lowest total demand reduction amounts to 1.35 MWh ($k=1$) and the highest 12.19 MWh ($k=0.1$). The demand retrieval ranges from 1.49 MWh ($k=1$) to 13.41 MWh ($k=0.1$).

Figure 10. DR operation for different levels of parameter k

4.2. Different PV share influence

The influence of RES share in the archipelago for different levels of flexibility was also part of the study. The PV share is observed as relevant to the total maximum load in the system. Thus, 25% of PV corresponds to the original share of PV (1 MW on bus 13 and 4.14 MW on bus 4). For purposes of this analysis, it was considered that buses 3 and 7 also have PV plants in order to avoid large amounts of curtailed PV production that would occur if all PV production is concentrated. In Figure 11 (a), it is possible to observe the cost reduction of the system operation as a function of the PV penetration compared to the original scenario A (with operation cost of 18,655.2 €). Increasing the share of PV in the system significantly decreases the operation cost.

Further savings are achieved for an increased level of flexibility; however, these savings are significantly lower than when more RES is introduced in the system. This result is justifiable because the assumed cost of PV generation is zero and an increase of DR level with the proposed model allows a better demand schedule depending on the market price. Moreover, Figure 11 (b) presents total curtailed electricity from PV that starts to occur in the case with 75% of PV share. Increased share of PV causes voltage issues (Figure 12 (a)). Thus, it is necessary to curtail PV production in order to maintain a stable operation of the system.

Flexibility increase results with the lower amount of curtailed electricity (Figure 11 (b)), which is expected as the demand can be increased during the periods of PV production.

Minimum and maximum voltage changes are presented in Figure 12 (a) and (b). Minimum voltage isn't significantly influenced by the increase of PV, while the maximum voltage increases from 1.06 p.u. to the maximum allowed value of 1.1 p.u. It is important to note that Figure 12 suggests that the voltage change is caused because of the PV share change in the system, while the flexibility does not have a significant influence on voltage change.

Figure 11. Operation cost reductions in comparison to the original scenario A (a) and total curtailed electricity from the PV (b)

Figure 12. Maximum (a) and minimum voltage (b) in the system

Moreover, the ESS and DR operation was more closely observed in Figure 13 for fixed $k = 0.5$ and different PV share in the system. The first observation is that the ESS operation for 25% and 50% of PV share does not differentiate, while it changes for 75% and 100% of PV share.

As PV share increases, the need for flexibility increases as well. Thus, the ESS, for scenarios with high PV share, adjusts its operation to prioritise the minimisation of PV production curtailment. The DR operation changes according to the day-ahead market prices. Thus its pattern remains approximately the same as in Figure 7.

However, between period 10 and 16, the DR model increases load when possible, which results in 138 kW of increased load. It is interesting to note that the increase of load (DR retrieval) occurs on buses 7 to 13, while the reduction (DR) at period 12 occurs for busses 1 and 2. In other words, the model increases the load on buses with the highest voltage, while it decreases the load on buses where voltage is less affected by the increased RES share. This result shows the benefits of the integration of the DR model in the distribution system grid is not visible in studies that aggregate all distribution system elements.

Figure 13. ESS and DR operation for $k = 0.5$

4.3. Price scenario analysis

In order to assess the sensitivity of the model, different market price scenarios have been modelled as described previously in the study. Modelled price values are presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Modelled prices on the day-ahead electricity market

With an increase or decrease of market prices, the total operation cost of every scenario increases or decreases which is expected as higher prices on the market will result in higher electricity import costs and the opposite for lower prices. Figure 15 presents operation cost changes over time for different prices on the electricity market and the lowest flexibility level. Greater changes in operation cost are visible only for the highest price scenarios, which are in correlation with results presented in Table 3 that show that the highest amount of DR occurs for that particular scenario.

Figure 15. The operation cost of scenario A and D for three different price scenarios

Table 2 presents total operation cost for all scenarios (A – D) and for lowest ($k = 1$) and highest flexibility scenario ($k = 0.1$). The operation cost increased as day-ahead market prices were higher. Scenario B and scenario C for the lowest introduced level of flexibility $k = 1$ do not

present significant operating cost reduction. However, for increased flexibilities, the operation cost reduces more significantly, especially for high electricity prices on the day-ahead market.

It can also be observed that the difference between scenario C and scenario D for the high level of flexibility does not differ significantly for any scenario of market prices. The highest difference occurs for the highest market prices amounting to 15.1 €. This indicates that the ESS does not have a significant effect on the operation cost of the system regardless of the modelled market prices, while the DR model enables higher savings, especially for the increased flexibility.

This result can be explained with the local impact of the ESS, while the DR is available in all buses of the observed distribution grid. Operating cost reductions are illustrated in Figure 16 as well, where it can be seen that the highest reduction occurs for scenario D and is equal to 258.67 €. The technical impacts of analysed cases are further investigated in the study.

Table 2. Operation cost for different scenarios under different flexibility levels in euros [€]

	Scenario A	Scenario B	Scenario C		Scenario D	
<i>k</i>	-	-	1	0.1	1	0.1
-2 σ	14,081.9	14,076.9	14,071.2	14,058.5	14,066.5	14,054.2
- σ	16,378.2	16,369	16,371.3	16,350.9	16,366.6	16,346.5
mean	18,665.2	18,657.2	18,659.8	18,615.4	18,651.8	18,607.8
σ	20,956.7	20,945.3	20,942.7	20,833	20,931.3	20,821.9
2 σ	23,247.6	23,231.6	23,197.1	23,004	23,181.2	22,988.9

Figure 16. Savings for different scenarios under different flexibility levels

The technical impacts of different market price scenarios can be observed in Figure 17 and Figure 18. The figures present voltage values for scenario C and D for three different market price scenarios. Figure 17 presents voltage changes at bus 10 for scenario C under the influence of different market price scenarios, while Figure 18 presents voltage changes at bus 10 for scenario D under different market price scenarios.

The results indicate that market uncertainty has a more significant impact on the distribution network technical constraints in scenario D in contrast to scenario C. The difference between the two scenarios is that, in scenario D, ESS is connected at bus 13. ESS operation is presented in Figure 19, from which it is possible to observe that the ESS operation changes under different price scenarios, which influences the voltage vector in the system. These results confirm previous results where it was shown that the ESS has a larger impact on bus voltages in contrast to the DR.

The comparison between scenario C and D observed in Figures 17 and 18 confirm this statement as it is obvious that higher voltage fluctuations occur for scenario D. Namely, maximum voltage deviation between lowest (-2σ) and highest market price scenario (-2σ) is 0.02 p.u. (0.2 kV) for scenario D, while, for scenario C, the maximum voltage deviation at node 10 is 0.004 p.u. (0.04 kV). Presented results indicate that the DR model can be implemented in the system without causing significant voltage changes in the distribution grid.

Figure 17. The voltage at node 10 for scenario C under market uncertainty scenarios

Figure 18. The voltage at node 10 for scenario D under market uncertainty

Figure 19. Battery operation for scenario D under market uncertainty

Table 3 illustrates the percentage of total DR used for each price scenario as well as the total available DR. The results indicate that different market prices influence different amounts of available DR, although the model does not decide on using the entire available DR at all periods. The results show that the activation of DR reduces by 0.31 MWh for the mean price scenario in comparison to the low-cost scenario and then again increases by 1.24 MWh for the high price scenario.

The maximum amount of DR is mostly determined with differences between the minimum and maximum price on the day-ahead market. Although used DR in the mean scenario is lower than in -2σ , this can be explained with the fact that the maximum DR possible is more than two times higher for -2σ prices than for mean prices, so the percentage of used DR significantly increases for mean prices in comparison with -2σ prices and continues to increase for 2σ prices.

Table 3. Available and used demand response for different prices for scenario D

	-2σ	mean	2σ
Used DR [MWh] (% of the maximum DR)	1.66 (13.96%)	1.35 (25.66%)	2.59 (33.26%)
Maximum DR [MWh] (% of the total demand)	11.9 (3.12%)	5.27 (1.38%)	7.79 (2.05%)

Figure 20 presents a detailed DR operation for different price scenarios. Figure 20 is in correlation with Table 3 as it can be observed that the available DR is least used for the lowest market prices scenario (a). The highest exploitation occurred for the highest market prices scenario and amounted to 33.26% of used available DR.

Figure 20. DR value for different price scenarios

Similarities between DR operation and battery operation can be observed in Figure 19 and Figure 20. At periods when DR and ESS can be used for cost reduction, the model is prioritising the DR as ESS is always available if there is a required amount for SOC available for a particular action. For example, Figure 20 (c) shows that the demand retrieval is active for hours 2, 3 and 4, or during the periods with the lowest prices, while the ESS starts charging in the third hour, which allows it to exploit the entire range of lower prices.

Similar can be observed for DR value at hour 11. The DR is fully active during hour 11, while the ESS is not, which saves the electricity for the ESS to discharge once the highest prices occur during night hours while the ESS operation. Without DR model, the ESS may or may not discharge at the given hour, but in either case, this would result in a higher cost because, or the potential to exploit higher price at hour 11 is not used, or the ESS will have less electricity in the evening hours during high prices. The prioritisation of the DR over the ESS occurs due to the losses of ESS cycling represented with efficiencies in the model in the equation (12). The utilisation of the DR model enables additional cost reductions, as well as profit generation for consumers as a result of the exploitation of exceptional electricity prices that occur on the day-ahead market.

4.4. Impact of different incentives μ

Several different values of DR incentives μ were considered for testing the sensitivity of the proposed model. The DR incentives vary from 5% of the market price to 20% of the market price. Each incentive value was considered under a different flexibility level. Figure 21 presents the operation cost of the system for different incentive and flexibility values. The results showed that when the incentive is set to 20% of the market price, the operation cost did not differ for different flexibility values, which means that incentive value should be lower for DR to influence system operation cost.

Flexibility factor values from 1 to 0.5 have no significant influence on the operation cost as it changes only for 9.4 € (from $k = 1$ to $k = 0.5$) with the incentive value of 5% of the market price. It can also be observed that as incentive value decreases, the influence of flexibility level on the operation cost is increasing. The model uses the DR service up to the point of $0.23 \lambda_t$ incentive value, which means that this is the breakpoint incentive for the analysed case. At this point, the total operation cost is equal to the cost of scenario B.

Figure 21. Operation cost for different incentive and flexibility values

Figure 22 presents the DR values (a) and percentage of used DR values (b) (percentage of total available DR) for the different flexibility and incentive values. The total DR values increase as the flexibility level increases and the incentive value decreases. Figure 22 confirms results from previous Figure 21 as incentive value has a more significant impact on the system operation than the flexibility level when k is higher than 0.25.

For example, for the 0.5 value of k factor, a decrease of incentive value from $0.15\lambda_t$ to $0.1\lambda_t$ resulted in 7.37% of increased used DR value, while the change of flexibility level from 0.5 to 0.25 for $0.15\lambda_t$ resulted with 0.61% increase of the same parameter. This result shows that, for

lower levels of available flexibility (higher k parameter value), incentive parameter μ should be used for increasing the DR value in the system. Increased μ would result in higher revenue for the consumers, which would further motivate them for investments in DR technologies.

Figure 22. DR value (a) and percentage of used DR (b) for different incentive and flexibility values

Furthermore, the results show that the DR values and used DR do not differentiate for cases when DR incentive is set to 10% and 5%. This result implies that the operation of DR does not change significantly when the DR incentive is reduced below $0.1\lambda_t$. Figure 21 also confirms this result as total operation cost does not increase significantly for the case when the incentive is set to $0.1\lambda_t$ in comparison to $0.05\lambda_t$, especially for higher flexibility levels.

The influence of different flexibility and incentive values on the minimum and maximum voltage in the distribution system was also observed. Figure 23 presents voltage values for observed cases.

Figure 23. Maximum (a) and minimum (b) voltage values in the observed energy system for different incentive and flexibility values

The results indicate that the presented DR model causes no problems for the DSO as both voltage values – maximum (a) and minimum (b) do not change significantly for different flexibility and incentive values. Changes can be observed when flexibility values increases and reaches a k value of 0.25 and incentive value μ reaches $0.1 \lambda_t$. Voltage value further changed when flexibility increased for k value of 0.1 and incentive value μ of $0.05 \lambda_t$, but this resulted in a maximum voltage change of 0.002 p.u. for both cases (a) and (b). This result suggests that the implementation of the proposed DR model wouldn't result in operational problems in the distribution grid for any flexibility and incentive level, which would result in the continuation of the distribution system stable operation.

Current study opens space for future research that will enable finding of the optimum incentive value. This value would depend on the objective function of the problem. One possibility would be to determine what would be the optimum incentive if the objective would be to maximise the DR providers' profit. Another possibility, particularly in high VRES distribution systems, would be to determine the optimum incentive if the objective would be to use DR for ancillary service provision.

This study observed the impact of different flexibility levels; however, it did not propose the method for determining the flexibility potential of the smart archipelago. Moreover, the study did not foresee the possibility for reactive power control, which will likely be necessary for future energy systems. . It should also be noted that the observed system was not designed as a microgrid, thus it requires the support from the mainland to preserve the stability. These remarks should be considered in future research.

5. Conclusion

This paper presented a novel DR mathematical model. The model was implemented in the small radial distribution. The DR model is a price-taker model based on the price differential between two consecutive hours and represents the increased or decreased share of the load in a specific hour. Providing a DR service to the grid results in revenue for the DR provider. This is also incorporated in the objective function of the optimisation problem. The model includes all grid parameters relevant for the distribution grid as well as the ESS model and two PV plants models.

- Even for the lowest levels of flexibility, the implementation of DR in the system results in a reduction of the operation cost and revenue for the DR provider. The

implementation of the ESS in combination with the DR model resulted in further savings increase.

- An increase in PV share in the system results in a lower cost of the system. When PV is at the 75% value of the maximum load, the PV production curtailment occurs. The curtailment reduces as the flexibility increases.
- The results showed that the market price has an impact on the total operating cost of the system as cost reduced as the market prices increased. The highest reduction of 258.7 € occurred for the highest market prices when the highest amount of flexibility was present in the system.
- It is necessary to observe both parameters – DR incentive μ and flexibility level k in order to optimally utilise the DR model. It was shown that there is no significant increase in DR value in the system when the DR incentive is lower than $0.1\lambda_t$, which leads to the conclusion that this should be the minimum value of the incentive. The breakpoint incentive occurs for an incentive value of $0.23\lambda_t$, after which the DR operation is not active. At the breakpoint incentive value, the total operation cost of scenario D is equal to scenario B.
- The implementation of the proposed DR model wouldn't result in significant voltage changes in the observed energy system, which leads to the conclusion that the DR model does not influence the safe operation of the distribution system run by the DSO.

Future research will be directed in investigating the possibilities of the DR and ESS combined operation when ancillary services are considered together with consideration of other grid management possibilities. Different possibilities for incentive parameters definition will be examined as well. The incentive can be defined as a function of production and realistic conditions in the electricity distribution grid, which would result in a more dynamic DR model.

Nomenclature

Indices and sets		σ	Standard deviation
i, j	Grid buses indexes	z	Observed data segment
t	Time period	\bar{z}	Mean value of observed data
$\Omega_{\mathcal{T}}$	Set of periods	$L_{i,t}^P, L_{i,t}^Q$	Active and reactive load at node i and time t
$\Omega_{\mathcal{N}}$	Set of grid buses	Variables	

Ω_{ε}	Set of lines	$\varphi_{i,t}^-, \varphi_{i,t}^+$	DR and DR retrieval values
Ω_{ESS}	Set of energy storage systems buses	$P_{i,t}^{PV}, Q_{i,t}^{PV}$	Active and reactive power from the solar power plant [MW/Mvar]
Ω_{DR}	Set of demand response buses	$E_{slack,t}$	Imported and exported electricity on the slack bus [MWh]
Ω_{PV}	Set of solar power plant buses	$P_{slack,t}, Q_{slack,t}$	Active and reactive power at the slack bus at time t [MW/Mvar]
Parameters		$E_{i,t}^{CPV}$	Curtailed electricity from the solar power plant [MWh]
β_i	Factor for limiting battery charge and discharge	$SOC_{i,t}$	State of charge of the battery [MWh]
$SOC_i^{min/max}$	Minimum and maximum battery state of charge [MWh]	$P_{i,t}^d, P_{i,t}^c$	Discharging and charging active power of the battery [MW]
η_c	Charging efficiency	$Q_{i,t}^d, Q_{i,t}^c$	Discharging and charging reactive power of the battery [Mvar]
η_d	Discharging efficiency	$V_{i,t}$	Voltage at node i at time t [kV]
$\Lambda_{i,t}^{PV}$	Maximum available solar power plant generation [MW]	$\delta_{i,t}$	Voltage angle at node i at time t [rad]
CPV	Value of curtailed solar power generation [€/MWh]	$I_{ij,t}$	Current from node over line ij at time t [A]
k	Flexibility coefficient	Abbreviations	
μ	Incentive for providing demand response [€/MWh]	EU	European Union
ϑ	DR retrieval coefficient	DR	Demand response
Z_{ij}	Impedance between nodes i and j [Ω]	RES	Renewable energy sources
θ_{ij}	Impedance angle between nodes i and j [rad]	ESS	Energy storage system
b	Line susceptance [μS]	PHP	Pumped hydro storage
$V_{min/max}$	Minimum and maximum allowed voltage [kV]	PV	Solar power plant
$\delta_{min/max}$	Minimum and maximum allowed voltage angle [rad]	DSO	Distribution system operator
$S_{ij,max}$	Maximum apparent power trough line ij [MVA]	CPV	Curtailed power value
λ_t	Electric energy price at period t [€/MWh]	NLP	Non-linear programming

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